

**CORRELATION OF USING TECHSPEAK TO THE SPELLING PROFICIENCY
OF GRADE 9 JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS ENROLLED IN STA.
PEREGRINA HIGH SCHOOL**

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Abstract

The use of mobile devices has generated a new way of communication by using unique abbreviations and grammatical shortcuts. This method of communicating has been commonly used by teenagers to socialize with other people in their generation. The use of these texts has alarmed parents and teachers. This study was conducted to discover the correlation of this method of communication called "Tech Speak" to a student's English proficiency. The researcher has surveyed grade 10 students, that has a total of 28 students, at Santiago National high school. The researcher used 10 words that are commonly misspelled as a parameter of the spelling test to measure the proficiency of both techspeak and non-techspeak students. The results yield an average of 8 and 7.7, thus making the students using Tech Speak more proficient in spelling than the students that are categorized as non-techspeak. The findings have led the researchers to conclude that the use of techspeak has no negative effects but rather it improves the student's spelling proficiency.

Keywords: *Spelling proficiency, Textism, Mobile Devices, University Students, Second Language Acquisition, Variables, English proficiency*

INTRODUCTION

The constant use of mobile devices by teenagers has fueled a culture of text messaging with abbreviations and grammatical shortcuts, which has parents' and teachers' attention. Does more frequent usage of text messaging lead to a reliance on these "textual adaptations" to the extent that it affects one's understanding of written grammar? The relationship between sixth, seventh, and eighth grade students' text message usage and their results on an offline, age-appropriate grammatical assessment test was examined in a survey (N = 228). The results demonstrate strong evidence for a general inverse link between the usage of techspeak in text messages and results on a grammar test, with implications for the Low-Road/High-Road Theory of Transfer of Learning and Social Cognitive Theory. These findings suggest that young people can learn by using communication technologies and that low-road learning transfer can be used to convert these new adaptations to standard English. According to Cingel and Sundar (2012), additional mediation analyses lead to the conclusion that not all types of textual adaptation are equally associated with grammar assessment scores. While "structural adaptations" were shown to be non-significant, "word adaptations" were found to be inversely connected to grammar scores. Texting, indeed, has become part of the daily lives of the people especially to the Filipinos. The Philippines has been tagged as the "texting capital of the world". Many Filipinos exchange text messages with the use of their mobile phones. People have become frequent texters, and they have started

sending messages in shortened ways. This problem cropped up with the innovation of this new technology, and its possible effects on the students' language proficiency. According to [van Dijk \(2016\)](#), children frequently utilize a unique form of register known as textese when texting their buddies on their mobile device. This register permits the usage of textisms, or instances of non-standard written language, like 4ever, as well as the removal of words (forever). Texts has a positive impact on children's literacy skills, according to earlier studies. Additionally, since texts frequently break grammar norms, it's probable that texts have an impact on children's grammatical systems as well. The major goal of this study was to find out if text speak affects how well children utilize grammar and whether this effect is limited to grammar or affects language in general. Additionally, studies on the impact of texting on children's cognitive development are still lacking. As a result, the secondary goal of this research was to determine whether textspeak has an impact on children's executive functioning. 55 kids between the ages of 10 and 13 were examined on a receptive vocabulary and grammar performance (sentence repetition) task as well as several executive functioning tests to find out more. Additionally, text messages from youngsters were elicited, and the percentage of omissions and textisms was calculated. After taking into account a number of other factors, regression studies revealed that omissions were a strong predictor of children's grammar performance: the more words children left out of their text messages, the better they performed on the grammar task. There were no other significant effects for measures of textese in the regression analyses, neither for the language outcomes nor for the executive function tasks, despite textisms' (marginally significant) correlations with vocabulary, grammar, and selective attention scores, as well as their marginally significant correlation with omissions' vocabulary scores. As a result, our findings indicate that textspeak has a favorable impact on children's grammar abilities. However, using text speak had little impact on children's executive functions, either positively or adversely. There remains much controversy about the effects that text messaging may have on the learning experiences of today's youth. In general, the use of text messaging has escalated due to the popularity and common use of cellular telephones. Although there is some research available about the topic, much more research is required to fully understand this growing technological phenomenon.

Background

As stated by [Rahman \(2016\)](#), Malaysian students' degree of English ability is frequently contested. The majority of Malaysian students still have trouble utilizing the language successfully, especially in tertiary education, despite spending nearly ten years in school learning English. Due to their limited English proficiency, many local graduates remain unemployed. The goal of this study is to look into the variables influencing undergraduate students at International Islamic University Malaysia's (IIUM) level of English proficiency. Data from a sample of 75 students were gathered using Google Forms after a series of questionnaires were made available online. The variables used were gender and years of English language study, two demographic parameters. The study's findings imply that the length of time spent learning English is more important than gender in determining an undergraduate student's degree of English proficiency. Language anxiety, students' attitudes, as well as peer, family, and instructor influences all had a role in the undergraduate students at IIUM's level of English proficiency. The study also showed that there is no connection between students' proficiency in second language acquisition and cultural prejudices.

Related Research and Ideas

According to ([Ahmadi, 2018](#)), technology use has grown to be a critical component of learning both inside and outside of the classroom. Most language classes use technology in some kind. Language learning has benefited from and been enhanced by the use of technology. Teachers can modify classroom activities thanks to technology, which improves language acquisition. Technology's significance as a tool to assist teachers in facilitating language learning for their students keeps growing. The use of modern technology in teaching English as a second or foreign language is the main topic of this study. It included several viewpoints that encourage English language learners to improve their technological literacy. In this paper, the researcher defined the terms "technology" and "technology integration," discussed how technology is used in language classrooms, reviewed prior research on the use of technologies to enhance language learning abilities, and made some recommendations for how to use these technologies more effectively to help students develop their learning abilities. According to the literature study, efficient use of modern technologies enhances language learners' abilities to acquire new languages. According to ([Akbarov & Tankosić, 2016](#)), technology changes the language we use and the contexts it makes possible as a communication channel. These days, information exchange and regulating interpersonal interactions are its main uses. The standardized language has been impacted by formulaic expressions and the variety of language we use on social media (Twitter and Facebook), thus some of the vernacular vocabulary used today is slowly making its way into dictionaries. The spoken word, or verbal text speak, was consequently altered by a written word that was supposed to be considerably affected. Social media jargon known as "internet slang" includes a variety of acronyms, language alterations, and paralanguage. This study looks at the history, evolution, and motivations behind Internet slang. Additionally, it aims to determine whether the presence of Internet slang improves or degrades the language. Also discussed is the idea of proper grammar in social media communication and how social media can help or impede good writing.

According to ([Wood C, Kemp N, Waldron S. 2014](#)), texting slang (also known as textisms) does not appear to have a negative effect on children's reading outcomes and may even help them improve their spelling abilities. Less consideration has, however, been given to how texting affects young people's and children's grammatical development. Therefore, this study looked at how children's and young adults' propensity to use incorrect grammar when texting interacted with how well they performed on formal tests of their oral and written grammatical knowledge, orthographic processing, and spelling abilities over the course of a year. There was no evidence of any negative relationships between the development of the children's performance on the grammar tasks and their usage of grammatical violations when texting, and zero-order correlations revealed patterns similar with prior research on textism use and spelling. The score on the written grammar test was positively correlated with adults' propensity to utilize nonstandard word forms (such as "do you"). For secondary school students, grammatical errors were discovered to be positively correlated with spelling improvement. Not all violations, however, were seen to be utilized consistently in samples of text messages collected 12 months apart or to be representative of text messages. The educational ramifications of these findings are examined, as well as the necessity of distinguishing between honest mistakes and willful rule breaking.

According to the study, the students' use of techspeak was determined using five different measures, which included:

- a. Use of textisms in formal versus informal communications
- b. Text speak proficiency: Translating Standard English to text
- c. Text speak familiarity: Translating text speak to Standard English (SE)
- d. Literacy processing speed: Speed of translation to and from SE
- e. Spelling errors: Translating target textisms to SE

In addition, the students responded to a survey related to their use of text speak in different contexts. In discussing the results of her study, [Sakota \(2019\)](#) says the high-frequency terms should be given priority while learning a foreign language's lexicon, according to recent research. However, it has been noted that lexical frequencies in textbooks, which are frequently the most familiar learning resources for students, vary slightly from those in general corpora. This study looked at the relationships between Japanese English as a foreign language (EFL) learners' vocabulary size, textbook frequency influence, and proficiencies to explore what kind of vocabulary—in terms of textbook and general frequencies—leads to higher proficiency in foreign language learning. This helped to clarify the effects of these two different frequencies. The findings demonstrated that terms that are often common but infrequently seen in textbooks greatly contribute to competency development and that those words separate learners with similar-sized vocabularies but distinct learning styles. Although the study did not reveal any negative correlation between texting and literacy, it was interesting that students own perceptions of the texting-literacy connection indicated that they thought it did. In terms of related ideas, some authors have offered interesting perspectives to text-messaging issues. For example, on the question of why text speak may not be as harmful, [Jamie McElroy \(n. d.\)](#) (<http://www.literacyconnections.com/blog/texting-and-literacy>) suggested that an inherent understanding of the correct use of the language forms must be in place in order for it to be deconstructed in the form of textese. Further that this phonetics are accurate representation of the original language. This writer offers the following as examples: so, called "vanity" license plate names use this form of linguistic deconstruction to convey unique and personal messages about the driver such as "L-VS-rks" (Elvis rocks) or 2-L8-2-DT (Too late to date). McElroy also stressed that in fact text speak may even be necessary because most cell telephones limit the allowed number of characters to 160 characters that requires the texter to condense the message that is sent. These examples demonstrate that language itself is dynamic and continues to evolve and change over time. The text speak that is in place today may give way to another form of text communication in response to the changing technology within which it resides. According to [Villines \(2012\)](#), in many respects, texting has facilitated communication by enabling individuals to bypass arduous phone discussions and making it much simpler to say "Hello" quickly. 72% of teenagers routinely text, and one in three sends more than 100 texts every day, according to the Pew Research Center. Young people clearly prefer texting to other forms of communication, and adults are following suit by texting far more frequently than they did only a few years ago. There is circumstantial evidence that texting is fast changing how individuals communicate with one another, both by text and in person, even though texting hasn't been around long enough for experts to examine its long-term consequences on communication.

Classroom Use

This next area of discussion might be coined --if you can't beat 'em, join 'em approach in the classroom. That is, classroom teachers are seeing the potential for text speak as a learning tool, resulting in the use of various forms of texting to connect students to reading and writing in the classroom (summarizing the classics into textspeak; demonstrating writing for a particular audience; as a tool for writing the first draft etc.) <http://www.surfnetkids.com/go/safety/672/lol-texting-and-literacy-in-todays-generation-text/> It should be noted that language is dynamic and changes constantly so teachers often make use of the different changes that occur. For example, teachers may allow students to begin by transforming the language of the classics to everyday lingo ("Friends, Romans, Countrymen, lend me your ears." Can be transformed to "Hey, y'all, listen up") Teachers can use the textese format to reinforce the idea that audience is one of the most important components in writing by having students write a letter to the editor of the local newspaper, then writing the same message in the form of textese. This also serves to demonstrate the idea of appropriateness. One does not dress in the same attire to visit an important dignitary as what one would wear to go to a backyard party at a friend's house. The most important thing is for teachers to provide students with real life reading and writing opportunities. According to [Oxford \(2019\)](#), using social media in the classroom helps keep students engaged and motivate them to contribute to the discussion. Teachers sometimes designate hashtags on Twitter or message boards for students to use when contributing to class discussions. For pupils who might not feel comfortable speaking in front of the class, this can be extremely helpful. By giving students materials to use on their phones to learn more about a subject, teachers can benefit from the use of mobile devices. This can include movies, articles from the news, forums, and more. Access to these materials during class time helps promote participation and conversations. Students who have access to cell phones can learn more and conduct further research while participating in class discussions. This is particularly valid for recent occurrences that haven't yet been covered in textbooks.

These examples are only a few of the ideas to apply text messaging in the classroom. As the interest in text messaging as a socially accepted tool for communication continues to grow, so may additional ideas for its use in the classroom continue to be prevalent. That is, teachers may benefit because students could stay interested in learning when they do not realize that real learning is taking place. This method of learning can be considered a form of "incidental learning", which is learning that takes place from other activities. Although this topic is not within the scope of this study, readers who wish to know more about incidental learning may access the following website: <http://www.calpro-online.org/eric/docs/tia00086.pdf>

METHODS

Research Design

This research paper is descriptive research where it aims to describe how using techspeak affects spelling proficiency by comparing the spelling scores between two sets of samples- techspeak users and techspeak non-users. To compare the scores of the two sets of respondents, the researcher used the formula of Arithmetic Mean.

Arithmetic Mean

$$A = \frac{S}{N}$$

where:

A = average (or arithmetic mean)

N = the number of terms (e.g., the number of items or numbers being averaged)

S = the sum of the numbers in the set of interest (e.g., the sum of the numbers being averaged)

Respondents of the Study

In this particular study, the researcher used the Grade 10 students at Sta. Peregrina National High school. There were 28 students used as the respondents of the spelling test, 18 of which don't use techspeak while 10 use techspeak when they text or chat.

Research Instrument

The researcher used the ten commonly misspelled words in English as cited by [Jenifer Calonia \(2022\)](#) as words to be spelled out in the test. The words are the following: Apparent, believe, entrepreneur, license, privilege, pronunciation, separate, tendency, weird, and weather.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

This part of the paper shows what the researcher found out in the study.

Spelling proficiency of techspeak users

Techspeak users	Score in the spelling test	Interpretation
1	9	Excellent
2	7	Good
3	9	Excellent
4	9	Excellent
5	8	Very Good
6	7	Good
7	9	Excellent

8	7	Good
9	7	Good
10	8	Very Good
N=10	Average= 8 Equivalent = 90	Very Good

Table 1 score in the spelling test of Techspeak users

This table shows that techspeak users got the average score of 8 which has the numerical equivalent of 90 and descriptive interpretation of Very good. [Moreover, Westwood \(2014\)](#) gives a very clear and succinct account of the critical abilities and procedures that support accurate spelling. He also outlines in very concrete terms a variety of evidence-based tactics and strategies that teachers can employ to help all students become self-assured, competent, and independent spellers. The book also discusses the objectives of various spelling skill assessments, including how they can inform lesson planning and instruction.

Spelling proficiency of techspeak non-users

Techspeak non-users	Score in the spelling test	Interpretation
1	9	Excellent
2	8	Very Good
3	9	Excellent
4	7	Good
5	8	Very Good
6	7	Good
7	9	Excellent
8	8	Very Good
9	7	Good
10	7	Good
11	9	Excellent
12	8	Very Good
13	7	Good
14	8	Very Good
15	10	Excellent
16	2	Failure
17	8	Very Good
18	9	Excellent
N= 18	Average= 7.7	Good

Equivalent= 87.7

Table 2 score in the spelling test of Techspeak non-users

This table shows that techspeak non- users got the average score of 7.7 which has the numerical equivalent of 87.7 and descriptive interpretation of Good. Though they are techspeak non-users their spelling proficiency is almost of range in terms of scores to those who are techspeak users

Participants	Score in the spelling test	Interpretation
Techspeak users	8	Very Good
Techspeak non-users	7.7	Good

Table 3 Comparison of the scores in the spelling test of the respondents

This table shows that as a whole, the techspeak users got a higher score than techspeak non-users. This is so because Techspeak users got 8 whereas Techspeak non-users got 7.7.

This would be explained by [Arellano et. al. \(2019\)](#) texting exacerbates people's writing indifference. The disturbing trend of text messaging's growing acceptance among students must be noted. The researchers found that adopting the shorthand way of writing when texting has a substantial impact on students' ability to accurately form simple phrases.

CONCLUSION

This conclusion can be made in the study:

1. Using techspeak has no negative relationship to spelling proficiency; but
2. rather it improves the spelling proficiency of the students.
3. The findings establish that the text culture of teenagers has positive impact of student's spelling proficiency.

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